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A COMPREHENSIVE PHYTOPHARMACOLOGICAL REVIEW OF *STEVIA REBAUDIANA*

Pankaj Khuspe^{1*}, Kishori Kokate¹, Trushali Mandhare¹, Ajay Kharche², Prashant Kumar Katiyar²

¹Navsahyadri Institute of Pharmacy, Naigoan, Nasrapur, Pune-412213.

²Ideal College of Pharmacy & Research, Bhal, Kalyan-421306.

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ABSTRACT

Stevia rebaudiana is known for not only its nutritional values but also for medicinal benefits. *Stevia rebaudiana* is one of member of the genus *Stevia*. In the era of synthetic medicine and excipients natural plants and their products can be used as sources of medicine & excipients. *Stevia rebaudiana* belongs to family *Asteraceae*. With varieties of chemical constituents *Stevia rebaudiana* consist of antioxidants like flavonoids and various phenolics, essential oils, tannins, etc. It is a natural source of steviol glycosides, like rebaudioside A and a potential source of prebiotics, with promising beneficial immunomodulating activity. *Stevia rebaudiana* is natural sweetener & is about 300 times sweeter than table sugar. Nutritional value of *Stevia rebaudiana* is beneficial for both the geriatrics & pediatrics ones. *Stevia* shows antiseptic, antiglycemic, antimicrobial, antibacterial, anticancer activity & also be used in indigestion, stomach upset, heart burn, weight loss, etc. It is expected hope for diabetic people who have craze to eat sweet. The aim of this review article is to describe systematic information with detailed exploration of pharmacological properties of *Stevia rebaudiana* which will provide a direction for further research.

Corresponding author

Pankaj Khuspe

Navsahyadri Institute of Pharmacy,

Naigoan, Nasrapur, Pune-412213.

khuspepankaj@gmail.com

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INTRODUCTION^[1-8]

Now a day's due occurrence of severe side effect from synthetic medicines people are moved to medicines obtained from natural plant as well as products obtained from natural plants. With reference to the survey of various worlds well renowned organization like WHO, about 75% of the world's population, mostly in below poverty line as well as undeveloped countries depend on traditional medicinal plant based medicines and their products for fulfill their health care needs. Medicinal plants are nature's gift to human beings to lead a disease-free, healthy life. Natural plants and products obtained from them act as a crucial role in not only nourishing as well as preserving health. The aim of this present review is to emphasis the phytochemical and pharmacologic investigations carried out on the plant, and to explain the multifarious role of this medicinal plant.

Stevia rebaudiana, is a naturally sweet plant without calorie content, becomes an effective alternative to sugar especially with in diabetic population across the world. *Stevia rebaudiana* is a tiny bush growing about 65- 80 cm tall, oppositely arranged leaves. Like other any vegetable crop *stevia rebaudiana* is a semi-humid subtropical plant that can be easily grown. The pH required for *stevia rebaudiana* plant should be 6.5-7.5; well-drained red soil and sandy loam soil. There is increase in demand for *stevia* plant in india for cultivation purpose. Diterpene glycosides can be obtained from *stevia rebaudiana*. The *Stevia* plant leaves of contain 9.1% stevioside, 3.8% rebaudioside A, 0.3% dulcoside and 0.6% rebaudioside C. From most of the previous study, *Stevia* has been reported to have no any adverse effect on humans. Recently *stevia rebaudiana* has found use in the food and pharmaceutical industries. Historically, *Stevia* is an endemic herb that grown in the highlands of Paraguay and the Brazilian for use as a sweetner and herbal remedies. The various name of *Stevia rebaudiana* are mention as following

Vernacular Names:

Hindi	: Meethi Patti,
English	: Sweet leaf, Honey leaf, Sweet herb,
French	: Stévia or Stévie,
Marathi	: Madhu Parani,
Sanskrit	: Madhu Patra,
Tamil	: Seeni Tulsi,
Telugu	: Madhu Patri
Common names	: sweet leaf of Paraguay, sweet-herb, honey yerba, honey leaf, yaawaan,

Figure 1: *Stevia rebaudiana* (Leaves, Flower, Fruit).

Geographical Distribution^[4-8]:

The origin of *stevia rebaudiana* is belongs to the northern regions of South America. *stevia rebaudiana* is still found growing wild in the highlands of the Amambay districts and Iguacu (area between Paraguay and Brazil). It is estimated that about 200 species of *Stevia* are indigenous to South America; however, no other *Stevia* plants have exhibited the same intensity of sweetness as *stevia rebaudiana*. *Stevia* is grown widely in many parts of Paraguay, Uruguay, Thailand, Brazil, China, Central America, and Israel

Taxonomical classification ^[1-8]:

Kingdom	: Angiospermae
Class	: Dicotyledons
Group	: Monochlamydae
Order	: Asterales
Family	: Asteraceae
Subfamily	: Asteroideae
Tribe	: Eupatorieae
Genus	: Stevia
Species	: rebaudiana

Plant morphology ^[4-8]:

Stevia is a perennial shrub that grows up to 1m tall and has leaves 2-3 cm long.

Leaves - Sessile Green in colour.

Odour - Odourless.

Taste - Sweetish

Size - 5 cm in length and 3 cm in width

Shape - Ovate

Extra features- Leaves acuminate petiolate, faces are glabrous

Flower - White.

Cultivation ^[9]:

Stevia rebaudiana is propagated mainly by stem cuttings procedure. Stem cuttings of plant should be 3-4 inches long and having two or three buds arises from plant axis. Rooting of plant can be increased by using various rooting hormones. Stevia prefers a well-drained fertile sandy loam soil high in organic matter. It prefers lighter acidic to neutral (pH 6-7) soil for better growth. It requires a constant supply of water but excessive amount of water causes stem disease. Stevia during very hot and long summer days requires shade. Summer season favors the growth of stevia. Temperature range required for plant is 24 to 35 degrees with suitable soil. It is a short day plant & flowering from january to march.

Chemical Constituents ⁽¹⁰⁻¹⁹⁾

Stevia rebaudiana consist of about different 100 phytochemicals. It is rich in flavonoids as well as terpenes. The stevia also consist of glycosides such as stevioside (6% - 10%) and rebaudioside-A (3% - 4%). Due to the non-caloric and sweetening properties, stevioside has increased their use. Other sweet constituents include dulcoside A, rebaudiosides A-E and steviolbioside,. Stevia has some bitter taste due to presence of tannins, flavonoids, essential oils. The other chemical constituents in stevia are: apigenin, austroinulin, avicularin, caffeic acid, beta-sitosterol, , caryophyllene campesterol, chlorogenic acid centaureidin, daucosterol, chlorophyll, cosmoiin, cynaroside, diterpene glycosides, dulcosides A-B, foeniculin, formic acid, , gibberellin, gibberellic acid, indole-3- isoquercitrin, acetonitrile, isosteviol, jhanol, kaempferol, kaurene, lupeol, polystachoside, luteolin, quercitrin quercetin, rebaudioside A-F, sterebin, scopoletin, A-H, steviol, steviolbioside, steviolmonoside, stevioside, stigmasterol, umbelliferone, stevioside a-3, and xanthophylls.

Table No: 1: Main antioxidant compounds of Stevia rebaudiana leaves.

Sr. no.	Group of constituents present	Examples
A	Phenolic compounds	Pyrogallol
1	Phenolic acids	4-methoxybenzoic acid
		4-coumaric acid
		4-methylcatechol
		Sinapic acid
		Cinnamic acid
		3-caffeoylquinic acid (3-CQA)
		5-caffeoylquinic acid (5-CQA)
		4-caffeoylquinic acid (4-CQA)
		3,5-dicaffeoylquinic acid (3,5-diCQA)
		3,4-dicaffeoylquinic acid (3,4-diCQA)
2	Chlorogenic acids	4,5-dicaffeoylquinic acid (4,5-diCQA)
		5-caffeoylshikimic acid
		5-feryloylquinic acid
B	Flavonoids	quercetin
1	Flavonols	quercetin-3-O- β -D-arabinoside
		quercetin-3-O- β -D-rhamnoside
		quercetin-3-O-glucoside
		quercetin-3-O-rutinoside
		quercetin-3-O-(4-O-trans-caffeoyl)- a-L-rhamno-pyranosyl-(1-6)- β -D-galactopyranoside
		kaempferol-3-O-rhamnoside
		apigenin
		apigenin-4'-O- β -D-glycoside
		apigenin-7-O- β -D-glycoside
		luteolin
2	Flavones	luteolin-7-O- β -D-glycoside

Pharmacological Profile

A scrutiny of literature gives some important pharmacological activities of the plant such as hypotensive, heart tonic action, antidiabetic, antimicrobial antioxidant anti-inflammatory, antihypertensive, anticancer, antibacterial, anti-lipid & anti-Obesity

Hypotensive actions ^[20]:

Stevia has hypotensive activity. Studies suggest that crude stevioside having antihypertensive effect on previously untreated mild hypertensive patient. The results suggest that oral crude stevioside is safe for tolerability during long term use as a sweetener in Brazil.

Heart Tonic Actions ^[21]:

Stevia shows heart tonic activity on smooth muscle of isolated guinea pig ileum by using a hot water extract of the stem of Stevia rebaudiana.

Antidiabetic Actions ^[22]:

Stevia rebaudiana Bertonni has been used in the treatment of diabetes in Brazil. The output of these stevia use shows blood glucose is decreased, ALT and AST, and increase in insulin level. Stevia leaves protect rats against diabetes, decreases the risk of stress and ameliorate liver and kidney damage.

Antimicrobial & Larvacidal Actions ^[23]:

Stevia rebaudiana shows antimicrobial properties that may influence the microbial flora populations in gut. Stevia rebaudiana extracts can inhibit in vitro the growth of *Candida albicans*, *Epidermophyton* spp., *Salmonella Typhimurium*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis* and *Trichophyton mentagrophytes*. The various research study also shows that, the antimicrobial activity of Stevia rebaudiana leaf extracts against a large number of microorganisms [*Streptococcus* (n= 12) and *Lactobacillus* (n= 4)] by the well diffusion method. In case of this zone of inhibition also studied.

Anti-diarrheal Actions ^[24, 25, 26] :

Tannins present in Stevia rebaudiana shows antidiarrheal action. Tannins are high molecular weight natural polyphenolic compounds having the ability to form insoluble complexes with proteins and digestive enzymes, etc.

Anti-inflammatory & Immune Modulation Actions ^[27]:

Taken together, our results suggest that anti-inflammatory effect of stevioside against the LPS-induced acute lung injury occurs due to inhibition of the NF- κ B signaling pathway. Stevioside may be used as a therapeutic reagent for acute lung injury treatment.

Anti obesity effect ^[28]:

This study suggested that effect of stevia extract on lipid profiles in C57BL/6J mice. For this purpose forty mice were divided into four groups: N-C (normal diet and distilled water), H-C (high-fat diet and distilled water), H-SC (high fat diet and sucrose, 1 mL kg (-1) per day), and H-SV (high-fat diet and stevia extract, 1 mL kg(-1) per day). Stevia extract has an anti-obesity effect on high-fat diet induced obese mice.

Anticancerous Action ^[29]:

The leaves of *Stevia rebaudiana* contains stevioside as a diterpene glycoside which shows the antitumour activity. This is the first report which indicates that *Stevia* is acting as anticancerous agents especially against the breast cancer.

Antioxidant Action ^[30-37]:

The effect of several extracts from the leaves of *stevia rebaudiana* on rat and mice was investigated. In the rat liver mitochondria stevioside, along with steviol, isosteviol and steviolbioside shows inhibition of oxidative phosphorylation. Stevia glycosides showed strong inhibitory activity against TPA-induced inflammation in mice. Due to presence of various chemical constituents like steviol glycosides, stevioside, dulcoside A, rebaudiosides A and rebaudiosides C stevia is showing anti oxidants action.

Clinical trials ^[38, 39]:

Various researchers conducted short and long term clinical trials on *Stevia* extract. The results of these show significant changes in electrolytes glucose, and insulin in healthy volunteers. Remarkable reductions in blood glucose occur in both anabolic and catabolic phases in patients. Two years long term study on mild hypertensive patients, stevia not only significantly decreased systolic blood pressure and diastolic blood pressure compared with placebo but also Quality of life was improved, and no significant adverse effects were noted.

Commercial preparations ⁽⁴⁰⁻⁴⁴⁾:**Table No: 2: Commercial preparations of *Stevia rebaudiana*.**

Sr. No	Product	Types	Manufacturer
1	Stevia	Crystal	At Stevia LLC
2	Stevia extract	Powder	Life Extension Foundation
3	JAJ Stevioside	Powder	JAJ Group, Inc.
4	Stevia Pure Powder Extract	Powder Extract	Stevia NOW
5	Stevia Liquid Extract	Liquid	Baar Products, Inc.
6	Stevia Dark Liquid Concentrate	Liquid Concentrate	Stevia NOW
7	Stevia Tablet	Tablet	Stevia NOW
8	So Sweet Sachets	Powder	Herboveda India
9	So Sweet tablets	Tablets	Herboveda India
10	So Sweet Leaf	Leafs	Herboveda India
11	So Sweet Stevia Liquid	Liquid	Herboveda India
12	Stevia Based Powder	Powder	Truvia® Company

CONCLUSION

Stevia rebaudiana leaves are leafy vegetable that belongs to family Asteraceae. The various important pharmacological activities of the plant such as anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, anti fertility, antihypertensive, antidiabetic, anticancer, antiseptic, Anti-lipid & Anti-Obesity activities. The chemical composition of leaves of the *Stevia rebaudiana* consists of glycosides, terpenes and flavonoids have been isolated from leaves & roots of sweet herb. Thus *Stevia* leaves are effective natural medication to develop new lead compound by clinical investigation. The medicinal applications of plant *stevia rebaudiana* and the countless possibilities for investigation still remain in relatively newer areas of its function. Hence, phytochemicals of these plants will enable to exploit its therapeutic use.

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